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Research Article

Role of Co-Curricular Activities in Behavior Formation of Students at Secondary School Level

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 21-May-23 Revised: 18-Jun-23 Accepted: 4-Jul-23 Published: 9-Jul-23	The study was conducted to check the role of co-curricular activities in students' behavior formation at secondary school level. The study descriptive in nature and survey method was used to collect the data. The population was all (302) the secondary level students of Tehsil Sehnsa of district Kotli AJ&K. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw the sample. Five-Point Likert Scale questionnaire was developed for students and teachers. SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) was used to examine the data in terms of frequency and percentage. It was found that co-curricular activities develop students' time management skills. Moreover, it helps students to complete their work within time. It is recommended that teachers may organize co-curricular activities on continuous bases for improving the students' management skills. It is also recommended that teacher may engage students in academic matter and teacher may polish their communication and collaborative abilities through co-curricular activities.
Keywords:	Co-curricular Activities, Students Behavior Formation, Academic Performance, Secondary School
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INTRODUCTION

The importance of education cannot be overstated because it is the only engine and foundation of the nation's development and prosperity. According to (Liu, 2021) some, education is generally viewed as a crucial weapon for change that is strongly related to a nation's overall social and economic growth. Activities that are not a necessary part of the regular academic program are referred to as co-curricular. Some institutions require participation in these events, while others only make a voluntary request. In addition to the regular academic program, all students in the school are required to participate in them when they are essential (Fulgence, 2015). Regardless of their level of effort, students in higher education who participate in extracurricular activities typically obtain academic credit. As a result, secondary school has a full program of extracurricular activities. There is a huge opportunity for education in these after-school program.

Co-curricular activities can be used to help students learn practical skills. Sports, competitions, athletics, exercise, yoga, and other extracurricular activities. These exercises offer the children a constructive way to channel their extra energy (Bhardwaj et. al, 2015). Their extra energy is put to good use and is profitable. Physically active students are more likely to lead moral lifestyles and accept moral principles. Co-curricular activities will aid in the growth of understanding at both the national and international levels. We can all agree that extracurricular activities support academic work, foster social and civic awareness, reveal latent talents in children of all temperaments, and help youngsters develop their full selves. Without them, students would just be bookworms (Ingale, 2014). Secondary education in Pakistan is heavily underfunded, and there are a number of issues as a result of a subpar curriculum, ineffective teachers, and a lack of resources (Saeed, 2022). The educational system in Pakistan has failed to cultivate students' aptitude for learning and confidence to deal with issues in daily life. The educational system disregards students' comprehension and intellectual development (Siddiqui, 2019). In Pakistan, teacher education programs have come under scrutiny for neglecting to take this into consideration, leaving teachers with the same conceptual thinking even after completing programs, claims (Sharar, 2020). Most educators rarely have the opportunity to review the curriculum and syllabus independently; as a result, for them, the curriculum is only represented in textbooks. Co-curricular events were regularly arranged beyond school hours even though they weren't as important to the school's operation as academic work was (Zeldin, 2016). Through participation in academic extracurricular activities, students are encouraged to pursue careers in subjects including painting, art, acting, photography, printing, and other related fields. Kids should participate in extracurricular activities since they develop a variety of skills through them. In today's culture, the importance of extracurricular activities has increased (Ordaz, 2021).

Co-curricular activities can mean a variety of things depending on the circumstance, the context, and the time of day. Even though they are not part of the academic curriculum, activities that are planned or approved by a school or college are still recognized as being essential to the operation of the institution. Sports, school bands, student newspapers, and other extracurricular pursuits are examples of extracurricular activities (Tyler, 2013). Co-curricular activities aid in the growth of secondary school people's positive character traits and abilities. Through these exercises, participants can learn the importance of perseverance, diligence, watchfulness, and the capacity to overcome challenges on one's own (Haensly, 2018). According to Muzaffar (2016), if kids are to become successful, responsible, and effective adults, both solitary and group activities for kids should emphasize cooperation, teamwork, and compassion. They develop social skills, leadership potential, as well as self-assurance and self-worth (Jaaffar, 2019). Students can mix their extracurricular and academic learning through these activities (Hwang, 2015). They hone their

social skills, leadership abilities, and self-assurance. Through these activities, students can combine their extracurricular learning with their academic studies.

Co-curricular activities can aid in the improvement and development of several mental and personality skills, including intellectual growth, social development, personality development, and moral development (Siddiky, 2019). These behaviors improve the surroundings by encouraging understanding thinking, tolerance, and cooperation. This can then lead to the development of a person's personality. Since it prepares students for either extra higher education or technical and vocational training and responsibilities, Pakistan's basic education includes the secondary level (Chamadia, 2018). Co-curricular activities can be utilized to teach students useful skills. sports, physical activity, yoga, and other extracurricular activities. The students can use these activities as a productive outlet for their excess energy (Bhardwaj, 2015). Their additional energy is used in a positive and advantageous way. The pupils' participation in physical activity helps them form wholesome habits and lifestyles (Mayes, 2015). Their extra energy is put to good use and is profitable. The students' involvement in physical education helps them develop healthy routines and ways of life.

Co-curricular activities have a big impact on students' earnings since they help and wrap up the entire teaching-learning process. It enhances classroom instruction and aids in the clarification of concept-related queries. In extracurricular activities, there is a strong focus on artistic and spiritual growth, both of which are crucial components of education (Hasanova, 2021). It fosters the development of skills like verbal fluency and improvisation. These exercises can be used to improve speaking, singing, acting, and recitation. Co-curricular hobbies are extracurricular endeavors that in some way enhance or supplement the curriculum outside of the classroom. Although not being graded or awarded academic points, they do provide some additional learning (Kemper, 2015). These extracurricular activities take place outside of the typical classroom and don't award grades or academic credit, but they do allow students access to supplementary and additional teaching. Co-curricular activities encourage cooperation, engagement, vitality, and optimistic thinking, all of which help kids develop their personalities and behaviors. Co-curricular activities assist students as they develop intellectually, emotionally, socially, morally, creatively, and as persons in a number of different ways. Every day, students are becoming more modern, and co-curricular education is losing significance at the secondary level.

Research objectives

1. To find out the prevailing practices of co-curricular activities for students at secondary level.
2. To identify the role of co-curricular activities in behavior formation students at secondary level.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Co-curricular activities

Any situation where children participate enhances their overall emotional, social, and personality development. Co-curricular activities enhance and engage the learning process, assist students understand the value of what they are studying, and help students learn more efficiently (Villalobos, 2016). Co-curricular activities support kids' communication, listening, ingenuity, and imaginative skills while also encouraging their innate ability and creativity. Also, extracurricular activities assist kids develop their moral character, social abilities, and personality as a whole. Co-curricular activities provide kids a sense of belonging to a community, teach them the importance

of belonging, and motivate them to attempt to help others who are less fortunate (Das, 2016). Children that participate in extracurricular activities learn team leadership skills, collaboration, co-operation, and healthy competition in addition to maintaining their physical fitness. Students' involvement in extracurricular activities at school contributes to the overall development of their personality. They provide children the ability to think critically and approach issues head-on (Acquah, 2014). Also, extracurricular activities provide kids with the knowledge and abilities they need to take initiative and be ready for their future goals. Therefore, it is impossible to overestimate the significance of extracurricular activities in a person's total personality development.

Importance of Co-Curricular Activities in Secondary School

Co-curricular pursuits happen away from the normal classroom setting. The academic program is supported by various extracurricular activities, which also assist students develop transferable skills including creativity, communication, teamwork, logical thinking, and critical thinking (Tang, 2020). A student's general personality, emotional development, and social development are all improved by participation in these activities. Co-curricular activities must be a part of a school's curriculum because they promote students' overall development (Mancha, 2016). They encourage the development of vital life skills and competencies required for a prosperous and fulfilling living. As a result, these activities are crucial for education in schools.

Enhances Overall Personality

The ability to take initiative and prepare for future endeavors is fostered in students through co-curricular activities and abilities (Keane, 2021). These activities help students develop their whole personalities by fostering the development of problem-solving abilities and by boosting language proficiency, teamwork, and public speaking.

Allows Students to Explore their Interests

As students participate in co-Curricular activities, they are exposed to a wide variety of options. Depending on this, students can also choose to develop and nurture their interests (Meiboom, 2015). Similarly, it also helps them identify and develop their qualities like public-speaking skills, leadership qualities, communication skills, and so on.

Develop a Sense of Responsibility and Confidence

When students are given tasks of responsibility at a young age, they become much better at handling similar situations in their later adult life too (Mansour, 2018). When students successfully handle responsibility, it fosters a sense of confidence and accomplishment. This also acts as a building block for personality development.

Improve Academic Performance

A side from the development of physical skills, comprehension skills, communication skills, time management skills, decision-making skills, they also build resilience in children (Opstoel, 2020). Take the example of sports - they will improve your child physical agility and focus but at the same time teaches them to work in a team, solve problems effectively and keep trying resiliently.

Create Opportunities

Better grades can make all the difference when applying for admission to other schools, universities, or institutions in this highly competitive world. Better possibilities are provided by co-curricular activities since those pupils who participate are given preference over those who do not.

Co-Curricular Activities and Academic Performance

Students are aware of the advantages of engaging in extracurricular activities and collaborating with their peers on schoolwork in order to develop their general skills and obtain practical experience (Jackson, 2021). Research on this topic, according to Boonk (2018), showed a positive association between extracurricular activities and academic success. Programs that are co-curricular frequently include components of the aforementioned tactics. The study concluded by explaining what success is by considering a student's behavioral aptitude, affective self-image, satisfaction, and cognitive grade point average. More capable students participate in more extracurricular activities than less capable students (Di Maggio, 2019). They don't have to stress that participating in extracurricular activities will consume all of their time and resources, divert them from their schoolwork, or anything else along those lines. They believe that their academic success has provided them with a wider safety net, enabling them to participate (Barclay, 2016).

Co-curricular activities are those that students take part in with the intention of improving their academic standing. They might also try to become friends with the instructors leading the activity as well as any other instructors who might be assigned to mark their other papers or provide recommendation letters (Rowntree, 2015). These children appear to understand how extracurricular activities might improve their learning efficiency, give them academic credentials, and open up career opportunities. Co-curricular activities appear to be more student-centered than traditional classes. Students assume leadership positions in co-curricular activities. Impulsive interests and immediate needs of students ascertain affiliations and experiences.

Co-Curricular Activities at Secondary Level

Activities that adhere to set lesson plans are classified as academic or curricular. Simply described, "curricular activities" are pursuits that happen in a library, lab, workshop, or classroom. The programmers' activities are a crucial part of the overall instructional plan (Kagoda, 2015). Because the teaching staff actively participated in the planning of these activities or program.

Classroom Activities

They are connected to activities that take place in the classroom, such as experiments, discussions, sessions, scientific observations, and the use of audio-visual aids, guidance programming, preparation for tests and assessments, and follow-up programming.

Activities in the Library

In order to prepare notes for class discussions, it involves reading books and publications as well as taking notes from needed and reference sources (Galvan, 2017).

Panel Discussion

The knowledge, comprehension, and experience of both teachers and students would have been improved by a panel discussion in the classroom. This program's structure encourages interaction between viewpoints on the subject being discussed (Simonson, 2019). It is important to stress that every academic or instructional activity in any topic will be useless without at least one of the concepts covered by the scope after detailing the various curricular activities.

Syllabus Committee

This organization is essential to guaranteeing the appropriate management of academic matters in educational institutions (Bordoloi, 2021). Senior academics from numerous disciplines make up this group. Its main objectives are to create the curriculum for the courses that will be studied

throughout the academic session and to decide the instructional plan for each class (Romiszowski, 2016). This group consists of senior professors from many disciplines. Its primary goals are to provide an overview of the academic session's course content as well as the schedule for each class's instruction.

Time Table Committee

The members of this committee are educators who have proven their efficacy, skill, and aptitude in developing schedules for educational institutions. The job of creating a new schedule for the future academic session has been delegated to this committee by the university president (Aithal, 2015). Before or after the educational facility reopened, the tasks on the schedule would have been finished. They consider the physical facilities available, the personnel position for teaching, and the principles of time table development while developing the schedules for various classes.

Institutional Planning

It is vital to highlight that each institution's development needs to consider the resources that are available to it. This committee's primary responsibility is to coordinate both curricular and extracurricular activities (Sumarsono, 2016). In terms of curriculum, this committee coordinates the activities of the committees responsible for proper academic or curricular programmed.

Guidance

This committee may also teach personal, educational, and vocational guidance to students in order to provide them with more knowledge and information about these topics (Nugent, 2015). This committee is led by the institution's head and consists of a counselor, a career master, and a teacher with an interest and area of specialization in guidance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was descriptive in nature and a survey was conducted to obtain information from the respondents regarding the role co-curricular activities play in secondary school students' development of behavior. All (302) secondary level students of Tehsil Sehnsa of district Kotli AJ&K were population of the study. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw the sample from the population. A questionnaire was developed for students for gathering information regarding co-curricular activities. A five-point Likert scale was used to take the responses of the respondents. The developed questionnaire was validated from two educational experts of the Department of Education University of Kotli AJ&K. The reliability of the instrument was measured by Cronbach's alpha statistical technique. The researcher was personally visited all the sampled schools and collected the data. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 23.0 version was used for the analyses of collected data. The researcher feed the collected data in SPSS data sheet and analyzed by using simple percentage, frequency and mean score.

RESULTS

Table 1: Mean analysis of Time Management Skills

Statements	N	Mean
Co-curricular activities develop students' time management skills	240	4.22
Co-curricular activities help students to complete their work/task on time	240	4.15
Co-curricular activities help students to focus their timely efforts on things that are important	240	3.81

Co-curricular activities develop time management skills in students through their trainings to progress in life	240	3.89
Co-curricular activities develop time management skill that students to better quality of life	240	3.71
Co-curricular activities help students to take immediate action for essential task	240	3.97
Co-curricular activities help students to manage their time in the best possible manner	240	3.97
Co-curricular activities help students learn to manage time more effectively	240	3.75
Co-curricular activities build better time management strategies for students to stay focused	240	3.75
Co-curricular activities encouraging students to manage their time with discipline	240	4.08
Co-curricular activities make students able to use their time effectively to get their work done	240	3.85

Table 1 shows the mean scores of time management skills. The table further represented that mean score of Co-curricular activities develop students’ time management skills; N= 240, M=4.22, Co-curricular activities help students to complete their work/task on time; N= 240, M= 4.15, Co-curricular activities help students to focus their timely efforts on things that are important; N=240, M=3.81, Co-curricular activities develop time management skills in students through their trainings to progress in life; N=240, M=3.89, Co-curricular activities develop time management skill that students to better quality of life; N=240, M=3.71, Co-curricular activities help students to take immediate action for essential task; N=240, M=3.97, Co-curricular activities help students to manage their time in the best possible manner; N=240, M=3.97, Co-curricular activities help students learn to manage time more effectively; N=240, M=3.75, Co-curricular activities build better time management strategies for students to stay focused; N=240, M=3.75, Co-curricular activities encouraging students to manage their time with discipline; N=240, M=3.75 and Co-curricular activities make students able to use their time effectively to get their work done; N=240, M=3.85. Furthermore, the results directed that Co-curricular activities develop students’ time management skills has the highest mean score in time management skills.

Table 2: Mean analysis of Social Interaction and Personality Development

Statements	N	Mean
Co-curricular activities improve the personality of students	240	4.38
Co-curricular activities help students to develop their intellectual abilities	240	3.89
Co-curricular activities provide a competitive teamwork environment	240	3.79
Co-curricular activities able students to prepare for their future actions/ life	240	3.87
Co-curricular activities develop leadership skills in students	240	3.82
Co-curricular activities build the strong foundation of a students’ character	240	3.89
Co-curricular activities make the students’ able to change their life style	240	3.79
Co-curricular activities enhance strong relationship among students	240	3.88
Co-curricular activities provide opportunities to students learn outside classroom environment	240	3.80

Co-curricular activities can help students to build social skills in everyday life by interacting individually or collectively	240	3.84
Co-curricular activities can help the students to provide an insight on their personality	240	3.98
Co-curricular activities improve social awareness of students	240	4.03
Co-curricular activities provide an opportunity for students to develop personal and social skills	240	3.87

Table 2 shows the mean scores of social interaction and personality development. The table further represented that mean score of Co-curricular activities improve the personality of students; N=240, M=4.38, Co-curricular activities help students to develop their intellectual abilities; N=240, M=3.89, Co-curricular activities provide a competitive teamwork environment; N=240, M=3.79, Co-curricular activities able students to prepare for their future actions/ life; N=240, M=3.87, Co-curricular activities develop leadership skills in students; N=240, M=3.82, Co-curricular activities build the strong foundation of a students' character; N=240, M=3.89, Co-curricular activities make the students' able to change their life style; N=240, M=3.79, Co-curricular activities enhance strong relationship among students; N=240, M=3.88, Co-curricular activities provide opportunities to students learn outside classroom environment; N=240, M=3.80, Co-curricular activities can help students to build social skills in everyday life by interacting individually or collectively; N=240, M=3.84, Co-curricular activities can help the students to provide an insight on their personality; N=240, M=3.98, Co-curricular activities improve social awareness of students; N=240, M=4.03 and Co-curricular activities provide an opportunity for students to develop personal and social skills; N=240, M=3.87. Furthermore, the results directed that Co-curricular activities improve the personality of students has the highest mean score in social interaction and personality development.

Table 3: Mean analysis of decision making

Statements	N	Mean
Co-curricular activities improve decision making ability among students	240	4.26
Co-curricular activities help students to decide their career choices	240	3.87
Co-curricular activities help students to make their personal decision	240	4.16
Co-curricular activities help students to make decision on logical grounds	240	3.92
Co-curricular activities develop making abilities among students for their better future	240	3.93
Co-curricular activities develop problem solving skill in students	240	4.15
Co-curricular activities can help students solve their complex situations	240	3.89
Co-curricular activities encourage students to think of various solutions about their subject difficulties	240	3.77
Co-curricular activities boost students to derive lessons in class decisions formed plan improvements to move ahead	240	3.72
Co-curricular activities develop a common sense for making decisions in life	240	3.78
Co-curricular activities develop students' ability to differentiate between options solve the problem best	240	3.85
Co-curricular activities enable students to think about analyzing any situation	240	3.83
Co-curricular activities allow students to face challenges in life through good decision	240	3.91

Co-curricular activities help students be more independent, responsible in life	240	3.89
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Table 3 shows the mean scores of decisions making. The table further represented that mean score of Co-curricular activities improve decision making ability among students; N= 240, M=4.26, Co-curricular activities help students to decide their career choices; N= 240, M= 3.87, Co-curricular activities help students to make their personal decision; N=240, M=4.16, Co-curricular activities help students to make decision on logical grounds; N=240, M=3.92, Co-curricular activities develop making abilities among students for their better future; N=240, M=3.93, Co-curricular activities develop problem solving skill in students; N=240, M=4.15, Co-curricular activities can help students solve their complex situations; N=240, M=3.89, Co-curricular activities encourage students to think of various solutions about their subject difficulties; N=240, M=3.77, Co-curricular activities boost students to derive lessons in class decisions formed plan improvements to move ahead; N=240, M=3.72, Co-curricular activities develop a common sense for making decisions in life; N=240, M=3.78, Co-curricular activities develop students' ability to differentiate between options solve the problem best; N=240, M=3.85, Co-curricular activities enable students to think about analyzing any situation; N=240, M=3.83, Co-curricular activities allow students to face challenges in life through good decision; N=240, M=3.91 and Co-curricular activities help students be more independent, responsible in life; N=240, M=3.89. Furthermore, the results directed that Co-curricular activities improve decision making ability among students has the highest mean score in decisions making.

Table 4: Mean analysis of Academic Performance

Statements	N	Mean
Co-curricular activities increase learning new activities of students	240	4.19
Co-curricular activities increase students' learning interest in the classroom	240	3.85
Co-curricular activities build competitive skills in students to promote academic performance	240	3.89
Co-curricular activities increase the academic level through different sport competitions	240	3.89
Co-curricular activities enable students to think critically and creatively	240	3.88
Co-curricular activities provide opportunity students to apply their knowledge to increase academic performance	240	3.88
Co-curricular activities make able to students' academic curriculum	240	3.80
Co-curricular activities develop students' holistic development for academic development	240	3.80
Co-curricular activities engage students to achieve a long run academic growth	240	3.75
Co-curricular activities help students to achieve better grades in exam	240	4.01
Co-curricular activities improve the class attendance of students' that leads to higher academic performance	240	3.91
Co-curricular activities develop discussion habits in students to improve their academic performance	240	3.94

Table 4 shows the mean scores of academic performances. The table further represented that mean score of Co-curricular activities increase learning new activities of students; N= 240, M=4.19, Co-curricular activities increase students' learning interest in the classroom; N= 240, M= 3.85, Co-curricular activities build competitive skills in students to promote academic performance; N=240,

M=3.89, Co-curricular activities increase the academic level through different sport competitions; N=240, M=3.89, Co-curricular activities enable students to think critically and creatively; N=240, M=3.93, Co-curricular activities develop problem solving skill in students; N=240, M=3.88, Co-curricular activities provide opportunity students to apply their knowledge to increase academic performance; N=240, M=3.88, Co-curricular activities make able to students' academic curriculum; N=240, M=3.80, Co-curricular activities develop students' holistic development for academic development; N=240, M=3.80, Co-curricular activities engage students to achieve a long run academic growth; N=240, M=3.75, Co-curricular activities develop students' ability to differentiate between options solve the problem best; N=240, M=3.85, Co-curricular activities help students to achieve better grades in exam; N=240, M=4.01, Co-curricular activities improve the class attendance of students' that leads to higher academic performance; N=240, M=3.91 and Co-curricular activities develop discussion habits in students to improve their academic performance; N=240, M=3.94. Furthermore, the results directed that Co-curricular activities increase learning new activities of students has the highest mean score in decisions making.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Co-curricular activities develop students' time management skills. Moreover, it helps students to complete their work within time. Co-curricular activities help students to focus their timely efforts on things that are important and also increase the time management efficiency in students to complete the essential task of education or personal life.
2. Co-curricular activities improve the personality of students. Moreover, it also develops the intellectual abilities of students at secondary level. Co-curricular activities develop leadership skills among students. It develops the student's character.
3. Co-curricular activities improve decision making ability among students. Co-curricular activities help students to decide their career choices. These activities encourage student's to take personal decision in life.
4. Co-curricular activities develop problem solving skill in students. Moreover, it helps student at complex situations. It also gives the different possible solution that students can solve the subject matter.
5. Co-curricular activities boost students to derive lessons in class decisions formed plan improvements to move ahead. These activities develop the common sense in students and also develop the problem-solving abilities between the students.
6. Co-curricular activities increase learning new activities of students. Moreover, it develops the competitive skills in students to promote academic performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Teachers may organize the co-curricular activities as continuously base for improving the students' management skills. It is also recommended that teacher may engage students to develop problem solving skill in academic matter, communication and collaborative abilities through co-curricular activities.
2. Teachers may motivate the students to participate in co-curricular activities for enhancing the academic performance. Moreover, teachers may organize different co-curricular events to encourage the students.

3. Teachers may provide the environment in school that students can involve the co-curricular activities for physical development. It is also recommended that they may provide healthy environment to the students so that they may self-relation and they may spend beloved life.
4. Teachers may develop the habits of co-curricular activities in students' for reshaping their personality. Moreover, teachers may build a communication with students that perform better outside the classroom.
5. Teachers may develop the leadership skills among students with conduct of co-curricular activities that make the students' decision power ability for their subject. Teachers may conduct different sport competition to improve the students' learning. It is also recommended that teachers may provide the opportunity to students perform their skills in practical platform.
1. It is also recommended that teachers may develop social skills competencies to students' help them interact and connect with the surrounding.

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